

Microwave-induced one-pot synthesis of pyrimidine-2(1H)-one derivatives as anti-inflammatory agents

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A series of pyrimidine-2(1H)-one derivative were obtained by multi-component one-pot synthesis under microwave irradiation. Equimolar quantities of ethylacetoacetate, substituted benzaldehydes and urea undergo condensation followed by cyclization in presence of aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide to produce corresponding pyrimidine derivatives. With the help of microwave heating, there is clean reaction with shorter reaction time, environmental-friendly, improved yield as compared to conventional heating method. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of their IR, NMR spectral data. These compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity. Some of them were found to possess significant activity as compared to standard drug.

Keywords: Microwave, synthesis, pyrimidine, anti-inflammatory agents, spectral data.

1. Introduction

The heterocyclic chemistry and its application for the generation of new biologically active compounds play major role in the area of drug development¹⁻³. Among the nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives possess wide spectrum of biological activities such as anti-hypertensive, anticancer, anthelmintic, anticonvulsant, anti-bacterial, antifungal, anti-tubercular, anti-diabetic, anti-Alzheimer, antiviral, analgesic and anti-inflammatory, etc.⁴⁻⁷. Pyrimidine is a six membered heterocyclic compound containing two nitrogen atoms at positions 1 and 3 of the ring with molecular formula C₄H₄N₂ as depicted in Fig. 1. Pyrimidine was first isolated by Gabriel and Colman in 1899⁸⁻¹⁰.

Fig. 1. Nomenclature of pyrimidine and its 3D structure with plane, centroid and exclusion sphere.

In the present work, the use of microwave heating method facilitates the synthesis of pyrimidine-2(1H)-one derivative with reduced reaction time, efficient rate of the reaction and high product yield. So, the multi-component one-pot synthesis under microwave irradiation is carried out by using equimolar mixture of ethylacetoacetate, substituted benzaldehydes and urea¹¹⁻¹³. These reactants undergo condensation followed by cyclization in presence of aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide to produce corresponding pyrimidine derivatives¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The newly synthesized compounds are characterized by IR, NMR data. The prepared compounds are subjected to *in vitro* screening for their anti-inflammatory activity.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials:

The chemicals and solvents used for the present study were of commercially grade. The melting points of the synthesized compounds were determined by open capillary tube method and are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesized

Fig. 2. Structures of some commercially available drugs containing pyrimidine moiety.

compounds and completions of the reaction were checked by TLC on pre-coated silica gel-aluminum plates (Type 60 F254, Merck) and were visualized by exposure to UV-light (254 nm) or iodine vapor. Ethyl acetate and n-hexane (40: 60) were used as mobile phase for monitoring TLC. The IR spectra of the titled compounds were recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer, model IR Affinity-1 (Schimadzu), using KBr powder and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra of the selected compounds were recorded on FT-NMR spectrometer; model Advance-II (Bruker), (400 MHz) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. The multiplicities of the signals are denoted with the symbols *s*, *d*, *t* and *m* for singlet, doublet, triplet and multiplet respectively. The microwave induced synthesis was performed in scientific microwave oven, Catalyst System (operating between 140–700 W). All the synthetic reactions were carried out at power level-2, which corresponds to 210 W.

2.2. Methods:

2.2.1. Conventional synthesis of 4-(substituted phenyl)-5-ethoxy carbonyl-6-methyl-pyrimidine-2(1H)-one (4a-f):

Equimolar mixture of substituted benzaldehydes (**1a-f**), urea (**2**) and ethylacetoacetate (**3**) in sodium hydroxide solution were refluxed on water bath for 2–4 h. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, ice cold water was poured into the reaction components followed by acidification with dilute HCl to get the solid product of pyrimidine derivatives (**4a-f**). The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.2.2. Microwave induced synthesis of 4-(substituted phenyl)-5-ethoxy-carbonyl-6-methyl-pyrimidine-2(1H)-one (4a-f):

The above reaction mixture mentioned under conventional

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of the titled compounds (**4a-f**).

synthesis, were subjected to microwave irradiation at power level-2 (210 W) for 6–12 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, ice cold water was poured into the reaction components followed by acidification with dilute HCl to get the solid product of pyrimidine derivatives (**4a-f**). The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.2.3. Biological evaluation:

2.2.3.1. Anti-inflammatory activity:

The newly synthesized compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity based following *in vitro* methods^{17–20}.

Membrane stabilization test:

Preparation of red blood cells (RBCs) suspension:

Fresh whole human blood (10 ml) was collected from healthy human volunteer who had not received any NSAID for 2 weeks prior to the experiment and transferred to the centrifuge tubes. The tubes were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min and the supernatant was carefully removed with a sterile pipette, washed three times with equal volume of isotonic saline solution and again centrifuged. The process was repeated three times until the supernatants became clear. The volume of blood was measured and reconstituted as 10% v/v suspension with isotonic saline.

Heat induced hemolytic:

1.5 ml of 10% v/v RBCs suspension was added separately to 1.5 ml of test, control and standard solutions. Here normal saline and Diclofenac were used as control and standard respectively. All the centrifuge tubes containing mixture of test, control and standard solution were incubated separately on water bath at 56°C for 30 min. At the end of the incubation, all the tubes were cooled under running tap water. Then all the incubated tubes were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 min and the absorbance of the supernatants were measured at 560 nm. The experiment was performed in triplicates for all the test samples. Percent inhibition of hemolysis was calculated by the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of hemolysis} = \frac{\text{Abs (control)} - \text{Abs (sample)}}{\text{Abs (control)}} \times 100$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis:

In the present work, different pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-one derivative (**4a-f**) were synthesized based on the multi-component one-pot synthesis under microwave irradiation. With the help of microwave induced synthesis, the rate of reaction was increased with improved yield and environmental-friendly reaction as compared to conventional heating method. For

Table 1. Physical data of newly synthesized compounds (**4a-f**)

Compd. Code	X	Molecular formula	m.p. (°C)	R _f	C		M	
					RT (h)	Yield (%)	RT (min)	Yield (%)
4a	4-CH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	180–182	0.64	2	65	6	73
4b	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃	172–174	0.76	4	69	8	76
4c	4-NO ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	190–192	0.59	3	58	7	64
4d	2-NO ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	212–214	0.56	2	65	10	67
4e	4-Cl	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	164–166	0.53	4	72	9	85
4f	4-F	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂	150–152	0.55	3	67	12	79

* C: Conventional; M: microwave

this purpose, various substituted benzaldehydes, urea and ethylacetoacetate reacted to undergo a condensation followed by cyclization in presence of sodium ethoxide. The chemical reaction followed Biginelli synthesis and afforded the targeted compounds.

3.2. Physical characterization:

The melting points of the newly synthesized compounds were determined by open capillary tube method and are uncorrected and were found to be in the range of 150–212. The TLC was performed using pre-coated silica gel-G of 0.25 mm thickness. The mobile phase used was ethylacetate and n-hexane (40:60). The spots were visualized in UV light and the R_f values were found in the range of 0.56–0.76.

3.3. Structural conformation:

The IR spectroscopy was performed with IR Affinity-1 (Schimadzu), using KBr powder and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . The stretching in the range $1422\text{--}1447\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1677\text{--}1723\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $3010\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3587\text{--}3611\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of C=C, C=O, Ar-CH, -NH respectively. The ^1H NMR was performed on Advance-II (Bruker), (400 MHz) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. The chemical shift (δ ppm) in the range of 7.10–8.70 indicates the presence of aromatic proton.

3.4. Anti-inflammatory activity:

All the newly synthesized pyrimidine derivatives (**4a-f**) were evaluated for their anti-inflammatory activity using membrane stabilization method. The results of this evaluation were compared with Diclofenac sodium, as reference standard. The anti-inflammatory activity results were presented in Table 2. All the compounds showed moderate to considerable activity as to compare with standard drug.

Table 2. Anti-inflammatory activity of synthesized compounds (**4a-f**)

Compd. code	Absorbance	% Inhibitions
4a	0.3769	54.57
4b	0.2270	72.64
4c	0.3425	58.72
4d	0.1862	77.56
4e	0.2106	74.62
4f	0.3169	61.81
Control	0.8298	–
Diclofenac (Standard)	0.1753	78.87

4. Conclusions

The new series of 4-(*p*-substituted phenyl)-5-ethoxy-carbonyl-6-methyl-pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-one derivatives were prepared based on the protocol of Biginelli reaction. The mixture of urea, ethylacetoacetate and substituted benzaldehydes were allowed to react in presence of sodium ethoxide under microwave irradiation. Microwave radiation has been applied as alternative energy source to accelerate the rate of reaction and improve the yields with formation of the pure products. The newly synthesized compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity *in vitro* by using membrane stabilization method (heat induced hemolytic technique). Most of the compounds exhibited promising activity due to presence of electron withdrawing groups at *ortho* and *para* positions of the phenyl ring of pyrimidine derivatives.

Abbreviations

Br: Bromine, Cl: Chloro, °C: Degrees Celsius, DMSO: Dimethyl Sulphoxide, F: Fluoro, h: Hour, HCl: Hydrochloric acid, IR: Infrared, KBr: Potassium bromide, *m*: *meta*, MCR: Multi component reaction, MF: Molecular formula, mg: Milligram, ml: Milliliters, MHz: Megahertz, MW: Microwave, NO_2 : Nitro, nm: Nanometre, NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance, NSAID: Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, OH: Hydroxy, OCH_3 : Methoxy, *p*: *para*, ppm: Parts per million, %: Percent, RBC: Red blood cells, R_f : Retention factor, RT: Reaction time, TLC: Thin-layer chromatography, TMS: Tetramethylsilane, UV: Ultra Violet, W: Watt.

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